

Quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR) studies on a series of off-target ion channel selective diltiazem sodium derivatives[†]

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Abstract : QSAR studies were performed on a series of off-target ion channel selective diltiazem sodium derivatives. Diltiazem sodium derivatives have been analyzed in relation to their physicochemical and molecular properties. The activities of the compounds were found to be significantly correlated with the physicochemical parameters such as MR, MW, Pc, $^0\chi$, $^1\chi$, $^2\chi$, $^5\chi$ and Xeq. It was found that the presence of group NH_2 at R₁ position was conducive for the inhibitory activity. The results are critically discussed on the basis of regression data and cross validation techniques. Poglani factor Q and the results of LOO (leave one out) method confirmed the reliability and predictability of the proposed models and it may be concluded that sterically hindered, denser and polar groups will favour the inhibitory activity (pIC₅₀).

Keywords : QSAR, diltiazem sodium, physicochemical properties, regression analysis.

Introduction

Diltiazem is a non-dihydropyridine (DHP) member of the group of drugs known as benzothiazepines, which are a class of calcium channel blockers, used in the treatment of hypertension and is also an effective preventive medication for migraine. It is based upon a 1,4-thiazepine ring. Diltiazem is metabolized by and acts as an inhibitor of the CYP3A4 enzyme. Diltiazem is prescribed off-label by doctors in the US for prophylaxis of cluster migraine. Diltiazem is used alone or together with other medicines to treat severe chest pain (angina) or high blood pressure (hypertension). High blood pressure adds to the workload of the heart and arteries and if it continues for a long time, the heart and arteries may not function properly. This can damage the blood vessels of the brain, heart, and kidneys, resulting in a stroke, heart failure, or kidney failure. High blood pressure may also increase the risk of heart attacks. These problems may be less likely to occur if blood pressure is controlled. Diltiazem is a calcium channel blocker. It works by affecting the movement of calcium into the cells of the heart and blood vessels. As a result, diltiazem relaxes blood vessels and

increases the supply of blood and oxygen to the heart while reducing its workload. Recent research has shown that diltiazem is able to reduce cocaine cravings in drug-addicted rats. This is believed to be due to the effects of calcium blockers on dopaminergic and glutamatergic signalling in the brain. Diltiazem also enhances the analgesic effect of morphine in animal tests, without increasing respiratory depression and reduces the development of tolerance. The current study represents the QSAR analysis of a series of off-target ion channel selective diltiazem sodium¹ derivatives using a number of structural parameters along with different indicator parameters at different substitution sites.

Results and discussion

The success of QSAR studies mainly depends whether or not the molecular descriptors chosen are appropriate to explain the biological activity. The present work deals with the QSAR studies on the series of 14 compounds that are off-target ion channel selective diltiazem sodium derivatives using steric and topological parameters along with indicator parameter and activity.

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

(I) Physicochemical parameters : The physicochemical parameters such as equalized electronegativity (X_{eq})² as electronic parameter, the steric parameters i.e. molecular weight (MW)³, molar refractivity (MR)⁴ and Parachor (Pc)^{5,6} were calculated by ACD Lab Chem Sketch⁷ and were used for the present studies and connectivity indices ($^0\chi$, $^1\chi$, $^4\chi$, $^5\chi$)⁸ were calculated by DRAGON Software⁹.

Molar refractivity (Mr) : Molar refractivity is generally considered to be a measure of overall bulk and is related to London dispersion forces as follows :

$$Mr = 4\pi N\alpha/3$$

where N is Avogadro's number and α is the polarizability of the molecule. It gives no information about shape and is generally scaled 0.1 and has been used in QSAR.

Equalized electronegativity (Xeq) : X_{eq} was evaluated using Sanderson's principle of electronegativity equalization. This principle can be stated as follows : when two or more atoms initially different in electronegativity combine chemically to form a molecule, they adjust to have the same intermediate electronegativity within the compound.

$$X_{eq} = \frac{N}{\sum V / X}$$

where, N = the total number of atoms in the species formula, V = no. of atoms of a particular element in the species formula and X = electronegativity of that particular atom.

Molecular weight (MW) : Molecular weight (MW) has also been used as descriptor, particularly in cellular systems, or in distribution/transport studies where diffusion is the mode of operation. According to the Einstein-Sutherland, molecular weight affects the diffusion rate. The molecular weight descriptor has also been an omnipresent variable in QSAR studies pertaining to cross-resistance of various drugs in multidrug resistant cell lines. $3\sqrt{MW}$ was used because it most closely approximates the size (radius) of drugs involved in the study of their interaction with GP-170.

Parachor (Pc) : The parachor may, therefore be defined as the molar volume of a liquid at a temperature at which its surface tension is unity. Parachor is obtained experimentally as follows :

$$Pc = \left(\frac{MW}{d} \right) \gamma^{1/4}$$

Pc is a molar volume term that is corrected by surface tension (γ) raised to the power $1/4$.

Molecular connectivity : The term molecular connectivity was adopted by Kier and Hall in 1975, in connectivity with a mathematical algorithm proposed by Randic. It is calculated with the help of DRAGON software.

Indicator variables : Indicator variables (parameters), sometimes called dummy variables are used in multiple linear regression analysis to account for certain features, which cannot be described by other variables. The indicator parameters (variables) are generally assigned only two values zero and one. It is taken as 1 (one) for that particular group or substituent and at a specific site in the molecule and 0 (zero) for all such cases where that group or substituent is absent¹⁰.

(II) Regression analysis : The regression analysis was done using SPSS 7.5 version software.

(III) Cross validation : As opposed to traditional regression method, the cross validation evaluates the validity of a model by how well it predicted data rather than how well it fitted data. For this analysis a leave one out (LOO) scheme was used in which a model is built for N-1 compounds and the activity for n-th compound was predicted. PRESS, SSY, R^2_{CV} and PSE were also calculated to confirm the validity of the models.

It is envisioned that this study will produce models that can be used for future designing of new analogues with higher potency. Here the biological activity (pIC_{50}) is a measure of inhibitory activity. In an attempt to determine the role of structural features, which appeared to influence the observed activity of reported compounds, QSAR studies were undertaken using linear free energy relationship (LFER) model of Hansch and Fujita¹¹. The multiparametric regression analysis used to derive the correlation was executed with the SPSS (7.5) programme. For QSAR studies, different analogues of parent structure and values of biological activity (pIC_{50}) along with calculated physicochemical parameters are reported in Table 1. The autocorrelation between all the structural

Table 1. Biological activities and physicochemical parameters of diltiazem sodium derivatives

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	MR	MW	Pc	Xeq	⁰ χ	¹ χ	² χ	⁵ χ	IR ₁	Observed pIC ₅₀
1.	-OH	-H	-H	-H	106.30	491.40	869.0	2.493	24.999	15.752	16.799	8.690	0	5.094
2.	-OH	-H	-H	-H	106.30	491.40	869.0	2.493	24.999	15.752	16.799	8.690	0	5.027
3.	NH ₂	-H	-H	-H	108.39	490.41	881.8	2.479	24.999	15.752	16.799	8.690	1	7.009
4.	NH ₂	-H	-H	-H	108.39	490.41	881.8	2.479	24.999	15.752	16.799	8.690	1	6.670
5.	-OH	-CH ₃	-H	-H	110.96	505.43	907.4	2.476	25.922	16.075	17.708	8.956	0	5.728
6.	-OH	-CH ₃	-H	-H	110.96	505.43	907.4	2.476	25.922	16.075	17.708	8.956	0	5.662
7.		-H	-H	-H	129.49	570.50	1051.1	2.466	28.819	18.808	19.310	9.885	0	6.223
8.		-H	-H	-H	145.05	628.58	1191.4	2.444	31.974	20.612	21.240	10.860	0	6.521
9.	-H	-H	-OH	-H	106.30	491.40	869.0	2.493	24.999	15.752	16.831	8.865	0	5.624
10.	-H	-H	NH ₂	-H	108.39	490.41	881.8	2.479	24.999	15.752	16.831	8.865	0	5.727
11.	-H	-H	NH ₂	-H	108.39	490.41	881.8	2.479	24.999	15.752	16.831	8.865	0	5.807
12.	-H	-H	-OH	-CH ₃	110.96	505.43	907.4	2.476	25.922	16.075	17.759	9.263	0	5.656
13.	-H	-H	NH ₂	-CH ₃	113.05	504.44	920.2	2.464	25.922	16.075	17.759	9.263	0	6.115
14.	-H	-H		-H	129.49	570.50	1051.1	2.466	28.819	18.808	19.341	10.121	0	5.622

parameters and biological activity (pIC₅₀) is shown in Table 2. A close study of this table makes it clear that those parameters which are orthogonal can be used together in multiparametric regression studies. These parameters have already been found to be useful in various

QSAR studies performed earlier¹²⁻²⁷ The aim of current study is mainly to study the role of different physicochemical parameters through linear models and their stepwise regression analysis is done by using indicator variable and different parameters.

Table 2. Correlation matrix showing correlation among various physicochemical parameters and inhibitory activity

	pIC ₅₀	MR	MW	Pc	⁰ χ	¹ χ	² χ	⁵ χ	Xeq	IR ₁
pIC ₅₀	1.000									
MR	0.326	1.000								
MW	0.269	0.996	1.000							
Pc	0.317	0.999	0.997	1.000						
⁰ χ	0.277	0.995	0.998	0.998	1.000					
¹ χ	0.272	0.994	0.997	0.993	0.991	1.000				
² χ	0.261	0.984	0.987	0.987	0.993	0.973	1.000			
⁵ χ	0.245	0.982	0.980	0.982	0.983	0.972	0.984	1.000		
Xeq	-0.531	-0.873	-0.837	-0.871	-0.858	-0.815	-0.880	-0.871	1.000	
IR ₁	0.714	-0.220	-0.256	-0.229	-0.264	-0.237	-0.301	-0.323	0.098	1.000

In this series, the following QSAR models have been obtained which are given below :

Linear QSAR models with Xeq, ⁰χ, ¹χ, ²χ, ⁵χ, Pc, MW, MR :

$$pIC_{50} = -22.593 (\pm 22.664) Xeq + 61.829 \quad (1)$$

n = 14, R = 0.531, R² = 0.282, R²_A = 0.222, S.E. = 0.496, F_(1,12) = 4.718, Q = 1.071

$$pIC_{50} = 0.210 (\pm 0.524) ^5\chi + 3.959 \quad (2)$$

n = 14, R = 0.245, R² = 0.060, R²_A = -0.018, S.E. = 0.567, F_(1,12) = 0.767, Q = 0.432

$$pIC_{50} = 0.110 (\pm 0.255) ^2\chi + 3.946 \quad (3)$$

n = 14, R = 0.261, R² = 0.068, R²_A = -0.010, S.E. = 0.565, F_(1,12) = 0.878, Q = 0.462

$$pIC_{50} = 0.016 (\pm 0.029) MR + 4.096 \quad (4)$$

n = 14, R = 0.326, R² = 0.106, R²_A = 0.032, S.E. = 0.553, F_(1,12) = 1.427, Q = 0.590

$$pIC_{50} = 0.002 (\pm 0.002) Pc + 4.155 \quad (5)$$

n = 14, R = 0.317, R² = 0.101, R²_A = 0.026, S.E. = 0.555, F_(1,12) = 1.344, Q = 0.571

$$pIC_{50} = 0.074 (\pm 0.162) ^0\chi + 3.941 \quad (6)$$

n = 14, R = 0.277, R² = 0.077, R²_A = 0.000, S.E. = 0.562, F_(1,12) = 0.997, Q = 0.493

$$pIC_{50} = 0.004 (\pm 0.008) MW + 4.056 \quad (7)$$

n = 14, R = 0.269, R² = 0.072, R²_A = -0.005, S.E. = 0.563, F_(1,12) = 0.937, Q = 0.478

$$pIC_{50} = 0.097 (\pm 0.217) ^1\chi + 4.272 \quad (8)$$

n = 14, R = 0.272, R² = 0.074, R²_A = -0.003, S.E. = 0.563, F_(1,12) = 0.957, Q = 0.483

Here and hereafter n - is the number of compounds, R -

is the correlation coefficient, R² - is the coefficient of determination, R²_A - is the adjusted R², F is the Fischer statistics^{28,29}, S.E. is the standard error of estimate and Q is the quality of fit^{30,31}. The resulting models were not found to be statistically good for better models, in statistical terms stepwise regression analysis was done.

QSAR models with indicator parameter IR₁ :

$$pIC_{50} = -25.834 (\pm 10.003) Xeq + 1.198 (\pm 0.364) IR_1 + 69.683 \quad (9)$$

n = 14, R = 0.936, R² = 0.876, R²_A = 0.853, S.E. = 0.216, F_(2,11) = 38.712, Q = 4.333

$$pIC_{50} = 0.456 (\pm 0.293) ^5\chi + 1.372 (\pm 0.528) IR_1 + 1.502 \quad (10)$$

n = 14, R = 0.874, R² = 0.763, R²_A = 0.720, S.E. = 0.297, F_(2,11) = 17.736, Q = 2.943

$$pIC_{50} = 0.220 (\pm 0.143) ^2\chi + 1.350 (\pm 0.528) IR_1 + 1.795 \quad (11)$$

n = 14, R = 0.872, R² = 0.760, R²_A = 0.716, S.E. = 0.300, F_(2,11) = 17.383, Q = 2.907

$$pIC_{50} = 0.024 (\pm 0.017) MR + 1.279 (\pm 0.521) IR_1 + 2.912 \quad (12)$$

n = 14, R = 0.869, R² = 0.756, R²_A = 0.711, S.E. = 0.302, F_(2,11) = 17.001, Q = 2.877

$$pIC_{50} = 0.003 (\pm 0.002) Pc + 1.285 (\pm 0.524) IR_1 + 2.932 \quad (13)$$

n = 14, R = 0.868, R² = 0.754, R²_A = 0.709, S.E. = 0.303, F_(2,11) = 16.863, Q = 2.865

$$pIC_{50} = 0.134 (\pm 0.093) ^0\chi + 1.310 (\pm 0.540) IR_1 + 2.181 \quad (14)$$

$n = 14$, $R = 0.862$, $R^2 = 0.743$, $R^2_A = 0.696$,
 S.E. = 0.310, $F_{(2,11)} = 15.901$, $Q = 2.781$

$$pIC_{50} = 0.006 (\pm 0.005) MW + 1.298 (\pm 0.553) IR_1 + 2.405 \quad (15)$$

$n = 14$, $R = 0.854$, $R^2 = 0.729$, $R^2_A = 0.680$,
 S.E. = 0.318, $F_{(2,11)} = 14.802$, $Q = 2.686$

$$pIC_{50} = 0.167 (\pm 0.131) {}^1\chi + 1.277 (\pm 0.564) IR_1 + 2.926 \quad (16)$$

$n = 14$, $R = 0.846$, $R^2 = 0.716$, $R^2_A = 0.664$,
 S.E. = 0.326, $F_{(2,11)} = 13.870$, $Q = 2.595$

In above shown models the sign of coefficient of connectivity indices (${}^0\chi$, ${}^1\chi$, ${}^2\chi$, ${}^5\chi$) is positive implying that larger groups with more branching should be preferred for the modeling. The coefficient of MR, MW and Pc are positive and therefore it may be suggested that denser and bulkier groups and polar substituents should have positive influence on the binding affinity. But the negative sign of Xeq in eq. (9) shows that less electro-negative group may be favorable for the activity. A very interesting and striking feature of the QSAR modeling presented in this manuscript reveals that everywhere the coefficients of I_1 are positive. This can be explained by suggesting that the presence of group NH_2 is conducive for the activity and therefore NH_2 group should be retained at R_1 position in the future drug modeling.

In order to examine the relative potential of models, predictive correlation coefficient (R^2_{Pred}) were estimated by plotting graphs between observed and calculated pIC_{50} values obtained with the help of model no. (9). The comparison between observed and predicted activities is listed in Table 3. Such correlations are shown in Fig. 1. From the Fig. 1 R^2_{Pred} values obtained for eq. (9) came out to be 0.876 and this is fairly high indicating the quality of the models. The calculated F value for these models is greater than F theoretical value [$F_{(2,11)} = 3.98$] for all the models and this fact also indicates towards significant correlation level.

Cross validation

Predictive ability was also evaluated by the LOO (leave one out)^{32,33} cross-validation procedure. This method systematically removes one data point at a time, a model is constructed on the basis of this reduced data set and is

Table 3. Comparison between observed and predicted pIC_{50} values for proposed model No. (1)

Sl. no.	Observed	pIC_{50}	
		Eq. (1)	Residual
1.	5.094	5.280	-0.186
2.	5.027	5.280	-0.253
3.	7.009	6.839	0.170
4.	6.670	6.839	-0.169
5.	5.728	5.719	0.009
6.	5.662	5.719	-0.057
7.	6.223	5.977	0.246
8.	6.521	6.545	-0.024
9.	5.624	5.280	0.344
10.	5.727	5.641	0.086
11.	5.807	5.641	0.166
12.	5.656	5.719	-0.063
13.	6.115	6.029	0.086
14.	5.622	5.977	-0.355

Fig. 1. A plot showing comparison between observed and predicted pIC_{50} values using model no. (1).

subsequently used to predict the removed sample. This procedure was repeated for all the points until a complete set of predicted values were obtained. The cross-validated R^2 in each case was found to be very close to the value of R^2 for the entire data set and hence these models can be termed as statistically significant. Various cross-validation parameters calculated for the proposed models are presented in Table 4.

Cross validation provides the values of PRESS, SSY and R^2_{CV} and PSE from which we can test the predictive power of the proposed models. It is argued that PRESS is a good estimate of the real predictive error of the model and if it is smaller than SSY the model predicts better than chance and can be considered statistically significant. Furthermore, the ratio PRESS/SSY can be used to

Table 4. Cross-validated parameters and predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) for the proposed models

Eq. no.	n	Parameter used	PRESS	SSY	PRESS/SSY	R ² _{CV}	PSE	R	1-R ²	PE	6PE
1.	14	Xeq	2.948	1.159	2.544	-1.544	0.459	0.531	0.718	0.128	0.768
2.	14	⁵ χ	3.861	0.247	15.632	-14.632	0.525	0.245	0.940	0.167	1.002
3.	14	² χ	3.828	0.280	13.671	-12.671	0.523	0.261	0.932	0.166	0.990
4.	14	MR	3.671	0.436	8.420	-7.420	0.512	0.326	0.894	0.159	0.954
5.	14	Pc	3.694	0.414	8.923	-7.923	0.514	0.317	0.899	0.160	0.960
6.	14	⁰ χ	3.793	0.315	12.041	-11.041	0.521	0.277	0.923	0.164	0.984
7.	14	MW	3.810	0.297	12.828	-11.828	0.522	0.269	0.928	0.165	0.990
8.	14	¹ χ	3.804	0.303	12.554	-11.554	0.521	0.272	0.926	0.165	0.990
9.	14	Xeq + IR ₁	0.511	3.597	0.142	0.858	0.191	0.936	0.124	0.022	0.132
10.	14	⁵ χ + IR ₁	0.972	3.135	0.310	0.690	0.263	0.874	0.237	0.042	0.252
11.	14	² χ + IR ₁	0.987	3.120	0.316	0.684	0.266	0.872	0.240	0.043	0.258
12.	14	MR + IR ₁	1.004	3.104	0.323	0.677	0.268	0.869	0.244	0.043	0.258
13.	14	Pc + IR ₁	1.010	3.097	0.326	0.674	0.269	0.868	0.246	0.044	0.264
14.	14	⁰ χ + IR ₁	1.056	3.052	0.346	0.654	0.275	0.862	0.257	0.046	0.276
15.	14	MW + IR ₁	1.113	2.995	0.372	0.628	0.282	0.854	0.271	0.048	0.288
16.	14	¹ χ + IR ₁	1.166	2.941	0.396	0.604	0.289	0.846	0.284	0.051	0.306

calculate approximate confidence intervals of prediction of new compound. To be a reasonable QSAR model PRESS/SSY should be smaller than 0.4. Also, if PRESS value is transformed in a dimension less term by relating it to the initial sum of squares, we obtain R²_{CV} i.e. the complement to the traces on of unexplained variance over the total variance. The PRESS and R²_{CV} have good properties. However, for practical purposes of end users the use of square root of PRESS/N, which is called predictive square error (PSE), is more directly related to the uncertainty of the predictions. The PSE values also support the quality of our models. The calculated cross-validated parameters confirm the validity of the models. All the requirements for an ideal model have been fulfilled by model no. (9), that's why, we have considered it as the best model. R²_A takes into account the adjustment of R². R²_A is a measure of the percentage explained variation in the dependent variable that takes into account the relationship between the number of cases and the number of independent variables in the regression model, whereas R² will always increase when an independent variable is added. R²_A will decrease if the added variable doesn't reduce the unexplained variable enough to offset the loss of decrease of freedom.

Predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE)

The predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE)³⁴

is yet another parameter used to decide the predictive power of the proposed models. We have calculated PE value of all the proposed models and reported in Table 4. It is argued that

- (i) if R < PE, then correlation is not significant;
- (ii) if R > PE, several times (at least three times), then correlation is indicated; and if
- (iii) if R > 6PE, then the correlation is definitely good.

For all the models developed the condition R > 6PE is satisfied and hence they can be said to have good predictive power.

Conclusion :

On the basis of the above discussions some general conclusions can be drawn :

- (1) Sterically hindered (more branched), denser and bulkier groups having high molar refractivity should be used in the future drug modeling.
- (2) The $\ddot{N}H_2$ group at R₁ site is preferential for activity.

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